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Issues and Challenges: Digital Payment System & Demonetisation in India

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Abstract

This research paper to explore demonetisation in India, digital payment system and the identify issues and challenges. The paper discusses conceptual framework, digital payment platforms, instruments and services available in the economy and their robustness. The article also defines strategies to overcome the challenges faced by the economy in digitizing the financial system. The present research paper is focusing on the impact of these new digital paymentsystems on customers and problems encountered if any.

Keywords:-Digital payment, . Cashless system, Online payment .Payment Systems, Mobile Payments, Demonetisation.

Introduction

Government of India on 8th November 2016, announced demonetization of old currency notes of Rs 500 and Rs 1000. The government came up with the idea long back and the process was done in phases from JhanDhanYojana to Income Declaration Scheme. Many people opened the account and some people declared as well. The amount collected was around 0.500 crore which was not enough as more than 4 lakh crore black money were prevailing in the country. Demonetization of 500 and 1000 notes compelled all the people to come in the system and deposit their money in their respective banks with a valid proof. Demonetization was done to get rid of the black money, corruption, terrorist funding, fake currency and reduce cross border terrorism.

The Government want people to disclose their black money and has created a situation where public is prompted to use digital payment channels for which the infrastructure already

exist. Due to less supply of small currency notes and restricted withdrawal of new currency, withdrawing cash has become difficult, there are long queues, people are forced to think of some other payment mechanism like going online or using mobiles or some other digital methods for making payment for their routine activities. This step is definitely going to boost the digital payment platforms and will drive India towards digital India. During this time government has also created awareness towards e-payment channels available to the public and has given boost to electronic payment private platforms.

India is still a developing country with a population of around 1.3 billion has more of its people living in rural sector where many of them are not educated and are not equipped with the modern facilities. The literacy rate of India in 2015 is just 74.04% which accounts that about 27 crores population of India is still illiterate. About 50% of the total workforce depends on agriculture which accounts to 13.7% GDP of the country are basically people living in the rural areas in the most backward villages without any of the facilities of irrigation, electricity, sanitation, medical services and even more important transportation. The internet user in India is seeing a rapid growth as it was 27% in 2015 to 34% in 2016, however it is not a good result as very few people from rural areas are connected to it. The mobile phone user is 54% which is very low compared to other countries.

Opportunities for Digital Payments

Digital payments in India is at nascent stage, and there is a push from varied quarters towards adapting the platform of digital payment solutions. Some of the reverent steps that has been incorporated in the recent past towards improving the scope of digital payments

1. Internet -Based payment system

There are four models of Internet-Based payment system:

1. e-Cash
2. Credit Card
3. Debit Card
4. Smart Card

2. Electronic Transaction-Based payment system

1. Secure Electronic Transaction
2. Cyber Cash
3. Net Bill
4. First Virtual Holdings

Conclusion

Demonetisation was done to curb black money in Indian economy. The biometric backed bank accounts not only makes the system fool proof but also serves as an excellent instrument for illiterate people to make payments with just their thumbprints. There are several problems for public to use cashless digital methods at present. There are low awareness, build trust, provide cyber security framework and provide necessary infrastructure to make it possible for public to adopt digital payment systems. Digital payment systems were existing earlier also in India, but now government is encouraging people to use digital mode of transaction rather than cash, because of limited supply of currency. The initiative by government to back the bank accounts by biometric aadhaar authentication numbers is a move which has lasting effects.

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